

Adolescents Positive Attitudes in Mosul, Iraq

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Abstract:

Background:

Adolescents is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. Positive attitude is a state of mind that allows adolescent to envision and expect good things. A positive emotional disposition toward the subject, a positivity that accepts the world as it is.

Objective:

To demonstrate the effect of advancing age on positive attitude.

Materials and methods:

A cross sectional study was conducted in Mosul city, Iraq. Adolescents aged 11-19 years were the target population. The age was classified into three categories: early (11 - 13 years), middle (14 - 16 years), and late (17 - 19 years). Rates of positive attitude among adolescents were presented in a table. The association was tested by chi square test.

Results:

Adolescents positive attitude (emotions, family cooperation, and coping with social demands) were increasing with advancing age.

Conclusions:

Advancing age affect positively attitude of adolescents (emotions, family cooperation, and coping with social demands) except healthy lifestyle.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescents is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. It involves multiple physical, sexual, behavioral, psychological and social changes. (1) Many parents worry that their teens might fall under negative peer influence or reject their family's values and beliefs, as well as are pressured to emerge in high risk and other negative behavior. (2) (3) Different people can have different attitudes towards the same thing or idea. (4)

Positive attitude is a state of mind that allows adolescent to envision and expect good things. A positive emotional disposition toward a subject is a positivity that accepts the world as it is. It is not a personality trait as an effort to pay

more attention to the positive things in life rather than the negative ones. This attitude allows them to stay optimistic and it's essential for happiness and progress in life (5).

The importance of positive attitude is that it determines the ability to grow, learn, and overcome life challenges. It helps in reacting to adversity, creating bonds with others, enhancing psychological well-being as well as individuals' subjective judgments (6-7).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross sectional study was conducted in Mosul city/Iraq. A total of 323 adolescents aged 11-19 years giving male to female ratio of 0.69:1 was participated in the study. A questionnaire with a known reliability and validity was used. It was distributed by Google form.

Adolescents age was categorized into early (11 – 13 years), middle (14 – 16 years), and late (17 – 19 years).

Chi square test was used to show the influence of dependent variable (attitude) on the independent variables (age group). P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

Figure 1 shows positive attitude among teenagers age group. Table 1 shows the distribution of positive attitude with adolescents age group. Positive attitude of emotions was found 26 (8%), 86 (26.6%), and 117 (36.2%) among early, middle, and late adolescents respectively. Positive attitude of healthy lifestyle was found 8 (2.4%), 25 (7.7%), and 21 (6.5%) among early, middle, and late adolescents respectively. Positive attitude of cooperation with the family was found 24 (7.4%), 99 (30.6%), and 103 (31.9%) among early, middle, and late adolescents respectively. Positive attitude of coping with social demands was found 23 (7.1%), 91 (28.1%), and 96 (29.7%) among early, middle, and late adolescents respectively.

Fig 1: Positive attitude among adolescents in Mosul

	Attitude	Early adolescent		Middle adolescent		Late adolescent	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Emotion	positive	26	70.3	86	53.4	117	93.6
	negative	11	29.7	75	46.6	8	6.4
	$\chi^2 = 55, d.f.=2, p = 0.0001$						
Healthy lifestyle	positive	8	21.6	25	15.5	21	16.8
	negative	29	78.4	136	84.5	104	83.2
	$\chi^2 = 0.8, d.f.=2, p = 0.7$						
Cooperation with family	positive	24	64.9	99	61.5	103	82.4
	negative	13	35.1	62	38.5	22	17.6
	$\chi^2 = 20, d.f.=2, p = 0.00004$						
Coping with social demands	positive	23	62.2	91	56.5	96	76.8
	negative	14	37.8	70	43.5	29	23.2
	$\chi^2 = 12.8, d.f.=2, p = 0.0016$						

Table 1: Distribution of positive attitude with adolescents age group:

IV. DISCUSSION

Adolescence is critical bridge between childhood and adulthood, and a vital period for positive life development, learning and growth.

Positive emotional attitude was 70.9% among adolescents. This might be explained by the fact that adolescence period is characterized by high emotional fluctuation (8-9) which in turn masks the adolescents' response.

The study showed that positive attitude about cooperation with the family was 70%. This high figure is inconsistent with that in literature (10). It might be attributed to forced weaning of the teenagers from peers after the conflicts. The virtual communication substituted the real communication. It differs from the real one, so the effect of

peers was nearly neglected. These might affect the future adulthood of Mosul. This phenomenon is unique. In Mosul, the conflict was post ISIS terrorism one. Resilience after ISIS terrorism was not studied yet in Iraq. Resilience after sectarian violence was studied in Baghdad. (11)

There was a significant increase in emotions, cooperation with the family, and coping with social demands with advancing age in adolescents ($p = 0.000, p = 0.001, \text{ and } p = 0.002$ respectively). The adolescent tries to get weaned from parents, wants to take his own decisions and play a dynamic part in things concerning his life. Late adolescence stage may characterize themselves as 'moody' i.e., they sway between positive and negative feelings in several situations (8-9). This finding is similar to that in Turkey (12).

The adolescents do better in school when their families are involved in their education. Students whose families take part in their education have higher levels of attendance, homework completion, academic results, and graduation rates. For adolescents who receive support by parents, peers, and teachers in academic problems or social relationships, their positivity is markedly high as it can offer them a positive contemplations of their lives and be optimistic about future and solving problems. This is similar to a study conducted in Poland 2008 (13).

Teenagers with positive perceptions had higher levels of life satisfaction and positive interpersonal relationships. It was also found that the perceived social support is a predicted factor for psychological well-being and had a significant relationship with social demands coping. This finding is similar to that in Norway in 2003 (14).

Healthy lifestyle was not affected by teenagers advancing age ($p = 0.669$). This might be attributed to poor interest for physical activity. It might be also due to reduced sleeping time and increase time spent on internet even at late hours at night. Fast food and snack unfortunately became part of daily teenager's life. This finding is similar to that in Qatar 2021 (15).

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